

EOM4SOIL

External organic matter for climate mitigation and soil health

WP 6 – Deliverable D6.2

Report on EOMs best management practices and practical guidelines for EOMs end-users

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Abstract

The EOM4SOIL project explores the use of external organic matter (EOM) as a soil amendment in agriculture. EOM includes urban and industrial bio-wastes, as well as farm-produced materials like crop residues and livestock manure. These materials often undergo processes such as anaerobic digestion, carbonization, and composting to create soil amendments that improve physical, chemical and biological properties of agricultural soils.

Research over the past two decades shows that using EOM in soil management preserves soil fertility and improves ecosystem functions. Without EOM, soil fertility can decline, limiting nutrient availability, and soil structure degrades reducing soil porosity, aeration and water capacity, with a direct impact on biodiversity.

The European Union promotes EOM recycling as part of a Circular Economy due to its benefits, including:

- Returning carbon to soils and potential carbon storage,
- Enhancing soil fertility and biological activity,
- Improving physical and chemical soil properties,
- Increasing nutrient use efficiency.

The present document provides best management practices and guidelines for EOM use, aiming to mitigate climate change and improve soil health, especially for arable and permanent crops. These guidelines are based on research conducted under various conditions and aim to increase soil organic matter content sustainably. The document offers also practical advice to ensure the safe use of EOM, preventing soil contamination and inappropriate management that could generate N leaching and greenhouse gas emissions.

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1. Introduction

The EOM4SOIL project focused on the characterization and use of external organic matter (EOM) as an agricultural soil amendment. EOM is understood as both (i) residue from activities external to the farm management cycle (urban and industrial bio-wastes) and (ii) produced in the farm (e.g. crop residues, cover crops, livestock manure and slurry). In both cases, EOM is subjected to transformation processes – anaerobic digestion, carbonization, composting, etc. – to produce amendments applicable in agriculture to improve the soil physical, chemical and biological properties.

Over the past two decades, research in agronomy and soil science has shown that agricultural soil management using various types of EOM can preserve soil fertility and improve soil ecosystem functions. Without them, there is a risk that physical, chemical and biological fertility of soils will be reduced, on the one hand limiting the availability of nutrients at times of increased crop demand, and on the other hand degrading soil structure, therefore reducing soil porosity and aeration, that are essential for maintaining biodiversity in agricultural soils, as well as limiting the soil water capacity.

The recycling of EOM on soils is strongly encouraged by the European Union as part of a Circular Economy, as far as there will be beneficial effects in terms of:

- carbon (C) return to soils and potential C storage after repeated applications,
- enhanced soil fertility in relation to soil biological activity,
- improved physical and chemical soil properties,
- enhanced nutrient use efficiency.

Best management practices and the associated guidelines for the use of EOM presented in this document are expected to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health, particularly those of arable and permanent crops. They have been compiled based on the outcomes of studies and experiments carried out by the research partners of EOM4SOIL project under different pedoclimatic conditions. The underlying objective is to provide operational guidance for a correct and efficient use of EOMs that aims to increase the organic matter content of the soil and improve its qualities for sustainable agricultural use.

The practical advice in the document is expected to facilitate the safe use of existing and new EOMs for the agricultural community, preventing soil contamination (due to their many different sources) and inappropriate management that could generate, among other things, an excess of nitrogen (N) that can be leached into soils and released into the atmosphere, as well as promoting green-house gases.

2. Types of External Organic Matter

Many of the EOMs produced can potentially be used as soil amendments, but in various cases the knowledge on their real agronomic value and potential environmental benefits and risks is limited. In EOM4SOIL a large variety of the most common organic wastes were considered for their use as a soil amendment with a view to mitigating climate change combined with maintaining soil health.

According to Deliverable D1.1 of EOM4SOIL project, the main EOMs produced in Europe can be listed as follows:

- a) Urban and industrial bio wastes
 - bio wastes from municipal solid waste, sewage sludge
 - agroindustry by-products,
 - industrial bio wastes
 - plant material and mulch,
 - wastewater,

- a) products and residues from the farm cycle
 - cover crops
 - energy crops
 - livestock manure and slurry

Given the volumes produced and the high moisture content of most of the EOMs listed, all these products are normally transformed into one of the following materials (even combined with each other) to be used as soil amendments for agricultural soils:

- compost (urban, mixed)
- biochar (mixed)
- anaerobic digestate (agricultural, urban, mixed)
- composted digestate (urban, mixed)

The production process of these products and their minimal characteristics are defined by Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising product. As organic soil improvers they shall contain 20% or more dry matter, at least 7,5% organic C and contaminants must not exceed the following thresholds per unit weight of dry matter (DM):

Element	Limit, mg kg ⁻¹ DM	Element	Limit, mg kg ⁻¹ DM
Cu	300	Ni	50
Cd	2	Pb	120
Cr(VI)	2	Zn	800
Hg	1	Inorganic As	40

Limits are also set for the level of pathogen bacteria such as *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli* and Enterococcaceae.

The use of EOM must also meet the requirements of Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 1991 on the amount of nitrogen (N) to be applied to the soil to prevent leaching into groundwater. The amount of soil improver to be applied should be planned based on an appropriate farm's fertilisation scheme.

3. Biochar

Biochar is a black carbon produced by pyrolysis – a combustion in a low or zero-oxygen environment – of organic materials that is mainly intended for soil amendment in agriculture. It has been increasingly promoted in recent years due to its potential to simultaneously address multiple issues associated with sustainable agriculture, including increase retention of mineral nutrients, long term (several centuries) soil C sequestration, reduction of nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and the production of biofuels as by-products of the pyrolysis.

3.1 Methods of production

Biochar is produced by pyrolysis at temperatures of 500-600 °C in specifically dedicated plants. After a reduction in size, the input materials undergo pyrolysis and are then cooled and made available for use. Once produced, it can be also mixed with compost or digestate at the beginning of their production process or before being applied to soil.

3.2 Use and prospects in agriculture

When used alone, biochar mainly performs as a soil amendment capable to retain several nutrients and improve soil physical characteristics. Mixtures with compost/digestate increase the fertilizing effect by favouring the binding of nutrients on the surfaces and/or their retention in the internal

porous spaces of the biochar. When used in the initial mix of the composting process, biochar accelerates the composting processes and reduces emissions of ammonia (NH_3) and N_2O .

In agriculture, biochar can be used in field crops, fruit orchards and vineyards at a dose of 20 t/ha when spread on the whole field surface, and 2 kg/m² when applied in a strip along the row. In field crops, it should be distributed before seeding and buried immediately to a depth of 20-30 cm with tillage operations. In plantations, it should be applied before spring vegetative growth on the inter-row or in a strip along the row. In this case sowing should be limited to a depth of 15-20 cm in order not to damage the root systems.

Application is done with a specific spreader or otherwise with a spreader for organo-mineral fertilizers adapted to the characteristics of for biochar. After the distribution on the soil surface, biochar is incorporated by tilling with harrows suitable for the given cultivation.

3.3 Practical tips for on-farm storage, handling, distribution and field application

Biochar is a highly stable organic material that can be stored cool in a dark place. However, it contains fine, sometimes dusty particles which can be a risk of fire. Therefore, it would be a commitment of the producer to provide biochar with an adequate moisture level to prevent fires and ensure proper application in the field.

It is then recommended to farmers to i) transport biochar in sealed containers; ii) wear suitable protective clothing when handling; and iii) limit the release of dust by moistening biochar before field application.

It can be applied to the soil in different ways. In arable crops the most common one is broadcasting on the whole soil surface. In permanent crops it can be also distributed on strips along the row or in the inter-row. In all cases distribution must be followed by a prompt burial of biochar to prevent loss through water or wind erosion. In grassland, experiments were also done using the practice of “top-dressing”, i.e. leaving biochar on the surface and entrusting macro/mesofauna for burial.

Biochar, especially that produced from materials with a high lignocellulosic content, can lead to a temporary immobilisation of N in the soil and, moreover, as it has a limited content of major nutrients, has a negligible fertilising effect. For this kind of biochar, the mixing with N-rich organic materials – for instance residues from bioenergetic processes, insect biomass, insect frass and microbial biomass – can be an interesting option to enhance its nutritional capabilities.

3.4 Constraints, obstacles and practical solutions

A critical point for a sustainable use of biochar is the distance of the pyrolysis facility to both the site/s of feedstock production and the places of field application. The problem could be minimized by building small on farm pyrolysis systems, which are currently still at the feasibility study stage. A further problem is its high price, partly due to limited production related to competitors for EOMs. Both limits in production could be solved in the future by investing in consortium scale and farm-scale pyrolysis plants capable of processing farm pruning and harvest residues.

Biochar with a small particle size and a high ash/dust content pose problem of handling, field distribution and burial uniformity in soils with more than 25-30% of clay (clay loam to clay soils). The best solution is the production of biochar into pieces a few centimetres size, which limits wind transport, and improves homogenization and ensures better “framing” of the soil structure.

Biochar is often rich in alkali that locally increase soil pH and soil salinity, therefore limiting plant growth especially in its early stages. The problem can be addressed by applying biochar some time before sowing/planting and mixing it well when it is buried.

In some crops – for instance leavy vegetables and grapevine – biochar negatively influences the initial growth due to poorly understood mechanisms. The problem can be solved by applying biochar a few months before sowing/planting.

Compared to mineral fertilizers, whose effects on crops are well known, the application of biochar to soil requires more experience, having to consider local soil/crop/environment combinations to maximize the positive effects and minimize the potential risks. A viable solution could be knowledge transfer to be entrusted to consultant services specialised in the topic.

3.5 Compliance with sustainable agriculture

As an EOM, biochar can promote the recycling of organic materials, particularly at a local level, and contribute to soil carbon storage, increase the water retention capacity of soil, enhance soil aggregation and boost crop yields when applied to poorly fertile soils. This results in decreased erosion and leaching and less energy required for mechanical operations.

4. Compost

The production of compost from the separate collection of bio-waste is an aerobic biological process that, under controlled conditions, transforms organic waste – mainly bio waste resulting from separate collection at source – into a material rich in stable organic matter and with a certain content of nutrients. Used as a soil amendment, it is fundamental for improving the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the soil.

4.1 Methods of production

Composting is carried out through a controlled, predominantly aerobic decomposition of biodegradable materials done by thermophilic bacteria. After collection and transfer to the composting plant, bio wastes are shredded to reduce the size of the collected materials. The composting process consists of two main phases.

Thermophilic phase

The aerobic decomposition performed by thermophilic bacteria gave rise to an increase in temperature of the composting material. Input materials are regularly and thoroughly moved and turned to ensure homogeneity and a sanitation temperature in accordance with the provisions of the Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, which requires the following temperature-time processing profiles:

- 70 °C or more for at least 3 days,
- 65 °C or more for at least 5 days,
- 60 °C or more for at least 7 days,
- 55 °C or more for at least 14 days.

Maturation phase

The temperature gradually decreases, and stabilization of the composted organic substances takes place.

In the end the compost is refined by sieving, with homogenisation of the composted mass and removal of any solid contaminants. Once refined, the compost can be sent for distribution to end users.

From a qualitative point of view the end-product of the process must be:

- stable, with very slow degradative processes,
- mature, without phytotoxicity,
- with a high content in humic substances,
- sanitised, with abatement of pathogenic and phytopathogenic charges.

The main technologies adopted are static pile, turned windrow, agitated bay, biocells and biocontainers. The main parameters regulating the process are C/N ratio, porosity, bulk density, water content, temperature of the composting material.

In the recent years there is an increasing number of plants that integrate the composting process with anaerobic digestion. In these plants, the organic matter in input undergoes an anaerobic digestion process. The solid digestate remaining at the end of the process is then mixed with green wastes rich in lignocellulosic component and subdue to aerobic composting. The liquid residue of the anaerobic digestion can be at least partially utilized in the composting process to maintain the appropriate water content of the composting material.

Specifically for the CMC compost, Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 sets criteria for compost stability and limits for macroscopic impurities (glass, plastic and metals), PAH₁₆ content and pathogens.

4.2 Uses and prospects in agriculture

From an agronomic point of view compost is comparable to manure, but present favourable characteristics such as low humidity and a higher content of organic C and N. This implies that the same supply of organic C and N can be provided with a lower amount of material, therefore decreasing the transportation and fertilization costs.

The application of compost has several agronomic benefits such as enhancement of soil structure, increased water storage and porosity, reduction of erosion, provision of nutritive elements that are slowly released, reduction of leaching, increase in the availability of elements, enhanced microbial life and suppressive effects of plant diseases.

Compost can be utilized in agriculture in different sectors:

- Arable crops: for maize, sunflower and beetroot it is usually broadcasted at the end of winter and before seeding, at a rate of 25-35 t/ha. For wheat it can be applied at a rate of 20 ton ha⁻¹ in summer/autumn.
- Permanent crops: before plantation compost is broadcasted at a dose of 35 ton/ha. In the presence of the plants, distribution it is carried out in autumn along the rows (1.2-2.0 kg m²).
- Horticulture and floriculture: application before tillage at a rate of 20-40 ton ha⁻¹.
- Turf grass: compost is indicated for the slow release of fertilisers.
- Mulching: especially indicated for young plants and after transplanting. Compost is applied according to the practice of top-dressing: it is applied without burying near the plants to form a layer of 8-10 cm thick and the application is repeated every 1-2 years. Compost as mulching agent limits weed development, maintains the optimal humidity near roots and increases soil organic matter (SOM) content.
- Growing media as partial substitute of peat: compost is indicated for the preparation of growing media for its low cost and great availability. It must have a great degree of maturity, i.e. absence of phytotoxicity and low values of electrical conductivity.
- Compost from green wastes can also be used in the formulation of organo-mineral fertilizers.
- Outside the agricultural sector, it can be used for landscaping and for environmental recovery.

Application is done with a specific spreader or otherwise with the manure spreader adapted to the characteristics of the compost. After broadcasting, compost is incorporated by tilling with harrows or subsoilers.

4.3 Practical tips for on-farm storage, handling, distribution and field application

Compost that complies with the quality criteria established by the law can be stored without problems provided if it is protected from humidity.

As for application in the field, there is a limited number of operating machines specifically dedicated to compost distribution, particularly those for application along the row. Farmers generally use manure spreaders not always suitable for compost broadcasting due to the different physical properties of compost and manure. The former is characterised by loose particles with prevailing small size, the latter has a lumpy consistency instead. This difference results in a scarce uniformity of distribution and a higher risk of PM10 emissions when compost is applied.

Specialized machinery for compost broadcasting are under testing in European and national projects. They will favour a more homogeneous distribution into soil, thus increasing the efficacy of amendment and decreasing fertilization cost.

4.4 Constraints, obstacles and practical solutions

The main constraints and barriers to widespread use of compost are the quality of feedstocks and end products, transport costs, process-related nuisance (odour), farmers' distrust of the product, lack of knowledge about the benefits of compost and how to use it, and lack of incentives for farmers that use it in their fields.

The low quality of input bio wastes is often related to the fact that source separation of organic waste is not implemented in all areas, or the collection schemes adopted are not very efficient. Of particular concern is the presence of non-biodegradable plastics in the input materials, which negatively affects the performance of the process and decreases the quality of the final products. Solutions are linked to policies aimed at improving separate collection at source, therefore improving the quality of raw materials for composting. Such policies may concern the definition of quality criteria for incoming organic waste, and campaigns to inform citizens about the importance of proper separation of municipal waste. In this context, an important role can be played by adequate information and activity in schools.

For farmers and users in general, dissemination actions are needed, also exploiting the great potential of social media, including networking activity and visits to composting plants, research centres and experimental fields to increase the knowledge about compost properties, modality of utilization and benefit. The mistrust of farmers and users in general can be overcome by producers adopting certification schemes and providing information on product traceability. For example, the voluntary certification scheme already operating in Italy (managed by the Italian Association of Compost Producers) currently only covers around 35% of the compost produced in Italy. Increasing the share of certified product would increase the quality of the product and the consistency of its characteristics, ultimately leading to greater consumer confidence in compost.

Compost is generally applied in large quantities per unit area (up to 30-40 tons ha⁻¹) and has a dry matter content lower than 70%. This, linked to the tendency to have few large composting plants, weighs on transport costs, which account for a large share of the entire fertilisation cost. This problem can be overcome by policies that favour the spread of small plants evenly distributed throughout the territory (local composting or community composting). Such policies have already been adopted but need to be more incisive. The spread of community composting is socially relevant as it increases the population's awareness of the importance of proper recycling of organic wastes.

A further problem may be the competition for bio wastes from anaerobic digestion plants. It could be overcome by integrating the two processes in the same plant. Integration increases the efficiency of the transformation of organic residues and leads to better odour control compared to composting plants alone.

Regarding the technological cascade, an interesting integration that deserves further research and implementation is the use of biochar in the composting process. The results obtained to date have shown the addition of biochar to the composting mixture can improve the process in terms of GHG emissions and N losses, and lead to a better quality of the final product. Furthermore, the integration

of a pyrolysis facility with into a composting plant can have a positive effect on the economic performance of the plant as the gas generated during pyrolysis can reduce the energy needs of the plant through the generation of thermal or electrical energy.

In addition to the beneficial agronomic effects, the management of SOM through composting has an important role in guaranteeing ecosystem services provided by the soil like decontamination from xenobiotics, reduction of harmful gas emissions and leaching, water regulation, reduction of erosion, compensation of the climate change, increase in biodiversity, landscape conservation. This means that farmers who use compost not only increase the fertility of their soils, but also improve environmental quality and social well-being. For these reasons, farmers who use compost should be compensated for the environmental and social impact of their behaviour, in addition to the economic return generated by the sale of the crop. Thus, there is a need for measures that recognize this additional value. The main obstacle to an effective implementation is the criterion currently adopted for the application of incentives, given by the quantification of the increase in organic C in soil. Such criterion is challenging due to expensiveness and the high spatial variability of soil properties. For such reason several researchers suggest linking incentives not on the results (measured increase of SOM) but to the activity performed, i.e. the adoption of well-defined soil management options scientifically proved to lead to the increase of SOM in the long period. This would simplify the procedure for compensations and encourage farmers to use compost as an amendment, resulting in a wider spread of this soil management option.

4.5 Compliance with sustainable agriculture

An increased use of organic residues avoids both utilization of non-renewable resources (e.g., fossil fuel, peat) and excess of energy expenses (i.e., production of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, treatment and disposal of organic wastes). Concerning sustainability of human health, appropriated SOM management through compost application enhances its ability to decontaminate the soil from xenobiotics and pollutants, reduce water pollution and increase the water quality of streams and rivers. The use of organic amendments avoids an improper and harmful fate to the organic residues, with indirect benefits for the human society.

From the point of view of economic sustainability, improved soil fertility by increased levels of SOM avoids excess energy costs for tillage, irrigation and fertilization because of improvement in soil structure, water holding capacity and fertilizer efficiency. In addition, adequate levels of SOM sustain high and constant productivity, reduce erosion and other degradative processes and eliminate the need for different and expensive solutions for the disposal of organic residues (Mondini and Sequi, 2008).

5. Digestate

Digestate is a by-product of the anaerobic digestion process, which produces biogas in sealed vessels where organic materials like bio waste, animal manure, and biosolids from wastewater are decomposed by microorganisms in the absence of oxygen. The main components of biogas are CH₄ (50-80%) and CO₂ (50-20%). The conversion of organic residues in methane is a process composed of 3 main phases: i) hydrolysis and acidification with formation of fatty acids, ii) acetogenesis with formation of acetic and formic acid and molecular hydrogen, iii) methanization with production of methane mainly by acetic acid dismutation.

The solid fraction separated at the end of the anaerobic digestion is characterized by a quite stable organic matter fraction that can be used as a soil amendment rich in nutrients or further processed as a feedstock of composting plants.

The application of digestate directly to soil has the potential to significantly increase environmental and economic values by reducing the use of mineral fertilizer, saving synthetic fertilizer costs, and restoring soil organic stocks [6,8].

According to Annex II of Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, input materials can be (a) plants or parts of plants grown for biogas production (CMC 4, fresh crop digestate), and (b) bio wastes resulting from separate bio-waste collection at source (CMC 5, digestate other than fresh crop digestate).

5.1 Methods of production

Anaerobic digestates are obtained through a controlled, predominantly anaerobic microbial decomposition of biodegradable materials which is done at temperatures suitable for mesophilic or thermophilic bacteria.

The organic materials mainly used as input are livestock effluents, sludges, agroindustry residues and energy crops like maize. Main technologies for AD process can be separated based on:

- Dry matter content
 - Wet digestion: DM<15%
 - Dry digestion: DM>15%
- Phase separation
 - Single stage, the phases – acidification, acetogenesis and methanization – occurs simultaneously in a single reactor
 - Two-stage: acidification and acetogenesis occur in one reactor, while methanization takes place in another one
- Feeding of the reactor
 - continuous
 - discontinuous

Source materials are regularly and thoroughly moved and turned to ensure homogeneity and the right sanitation temperature. The Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 prescribes a thermophilic (55 °C) or mesophilic (37-40 °C) anaerobic digestion with a treatment process including pasteurisation or otherwise followed by composting of the solid digestate in accordance with one of the following temperature-time processing profiles:

- 70 °C or more for at least 3 days,
- 65 °C or more for at least 5 days,
- 60 °C or more for at least 7 days,
- 55 °C or more for at least 14 days.

Specifically for the CMC 5, Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 sets further limits for macroscopic impurities (glass, plastic and metals) and PAH₁₆ content.

Anaerobic digestion leads to major changes in the organic and mineral components of the organic materials subjected to the process. Regarding the organic components, there is a reduction in the more labile components (proteins, sugars, lipids) and an increase in the more recalcitrant fractions (lignin and lignin-cellulose components). This transformation leads to a material with a stability close to that of composting. The main difference between compost and digestate is that compost is rich in humified components while digestate has a certain fraction of lipid.

In in-farm anaerobic digestion plants, the digestate often undergoes a liquid/solid separation. The solid fraction represents no more than 10-15 % of the total digestate weight, it has a dry matter content larger than 20% and concentrates the organic fraction, organic N and P. The liquid fraction consists of 85-90% of the digestate volume and contains all soluble composts, among them ammonium.

If composted, the digestate contains 20% or more dry matter having more than 70% SOM and generally containing 4-10 kg/t of N in a predominantly organic form.

5.2 Use and prospects in agriculture

From an agronomic point of view, solid digestate is an amendment that helps maintain the soil microbial community and soil organic matter content.

Due to the prevalent presence of organic N, it also releases N in a gradual manner thus reducing leaching towards the groundwater. Digestate is also relevant for its fertilising properties, for its content of nutrients useful for plant mineral nutrition. Anaerobic digestion leads to the partial mineralisation of organic N with the production of ammonium that is readily available to plants. The total N content of the digestate is between 5 and 10% (on a dry matter basis). The percentage of NH₃ content can reach 60% of the total nitrogen and qualifies the digestate as an effective fertiliser. However, the significant content of organic N (40% of total N), which is released slowly and gradually, reduces the risk of N leaching to groundwater.

Anaerobic digestate contains significant amounts of P (0.6-1.5%) and K (2.5-3.3%). Since available P is 40% of total P content and all K present is available, digestate could completely replace mineral fertilisers. The digestate is usually applied before ploughing in arable crops, and before tillage in permanent and horticultural crops. Since it has a certain amount of total N, the applicable dose must take account of the recommendations of the Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 1991 and, especially for field crops, must be planned according to the farm's fertilization scheme.

5.3 Practical tips for on-farm storage, handling, distribution and field application

The distribution of liquid digestates generally takes place with slurry spreaders. To limit NH₃ emissions, a fast incorporation into the first centimetres of soil should be provided. The most innovative fertiliser spreaders are equipped with a direct digestate injection system into the soil. A further innovative distribution system is the umbilical system in which a long tube connects the digestate depot, located at the edge of the field, to the tractor that distributes and incorporates the digestate into the soil.

Solid digestate complying with the quality criteria established by the law can be stored in a dedicated place in form of piles covered to protect them from rain. A regular monitoring of storage conditions until digestate application is also required to avoid degradation and the loss of material from the storage location. In any case, it is advisable to wear suitable protective clothing during handling.

As with compost, also in the case of solid digestate there are a few specifically dedicated spreaders on the market and farmers must adapt their manure spreaders to consider the different physical properties of digestate and manure and avoid uneven distribution. After the distribution on the soil, the digestate is buried by tilling.

Due to its relatively high N content, digestate is the EOM most affected by the recommendations of Council Directive 91/676/EEC about the quantities that may be spread annually on land. In areas that are vulnerable to pollution by N compounds, the dose must be determined based on the analytical data for each individual batch supplied by the anaerobic digestion plant, so as not to exceed the limit value that can be distributed in total on the farm by fertilisation and soil amendment.

5.4 Constraints, obstacles and practical solutions

Even in the case of digestate, a critical point is conveyance expenses due to the distance of anaerobic digestion facility from the site/s of feedstock production and the place of use. The problem is minimal in the case of plants purposively located in livestock farms. In this case, even the transport of feedstock to the plant has a reduced cost, largely offset by the reduction in the volumes of bio waste produced at the end of the digestion process.

The digestate exits anaerobic digestion plants with sanitary characteristics suitable for its use in agriculture but may harbour the presence of bacteria of the *Clostridiaceae* family (resilient in anaerobic

digestion systems) that can produce metabolites detrimental for the quality of cheese during the aging phase. Consequently, the frequency of use of digestate in forage crops should be limited in the soils of dairy farms included in the dairy industry supply chain.

As previously pointed out, digestate could result in nitrate leaching to water and ammonia emissions to the atmosphere. The problem of N leaching is strictly regulated by the EU by being addressed through farm planning of fertilisation and amendment. As for ammonia, on the other hand, it is important to adequately manage digestate broadcasting by quick burial after application.

A general solution to the listed problems is to adequately inform farmers, agronomists, and stakeholders about the benefits, challenges, and best practices associated with digestate application.

5.5 Compliance with sustainable agriculture

As with biochar and compost, the main benefit of digestate is the reduction in the use of both non-renewable resources and energy costs. Further advantages for agricultural sustainability are given using a stabilized and sanitized material that provides a good contribution of organic matter to soil and allows to reduce, both in the production phase and in the subsequent distribution to the soil, the emissions of greenhouse gases.

From the point of view of economic sustainability, the digestate, in addition to preserving/increasing the soil organic matter, provides nutrients such as N, P and K which allow to limit the use of mineral fertilizers, reducing the related economic and environmental production costs.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

6.1 Major take-home messages to stakeholders

- The **repeated application** of EOM **increases organic matter content and C sequestration** in soil
- EOMs **improve soil aggregation, increasing macroporosity and the soil physical fertility**
- **Improved air and water movement** in the ploughed horizon **increases biological activity and biodiversity of agricultural soils**
- **EOMs increase soil fertility and crop productivity**, therefore reducing the use of mineral fertilizer and **increasing nutrient use efficiency**
- EOMs **best management practices also improve the GHG balance** compared to mineral fertilizers
- Beside agronomical benefits, **EOM recovers, maintains and enhances SOM**, which is **pivotal in assuring proper soil functioning and ecosystems services**
- **EOM recovers nutrients and organic matter from organic residues and recycle them into the soil closing elements cycle and fostering the transition towards a circular economy**
- **Quality control** of EOM **make possible their safe use.**
- **Combined, field experiments and knowledge of farmers are fundamental to improve the EOM management.**

The relative effect of EOMs on properties related to soil environmental sustainability at glance.

Processed EOM	C sequestration	Nutrient supply (N, P, K)	GHG emission reduction	Biological activity
Biochar	+++	+	++	+
Compost	++	++	++	++
Digestate	+	+++	+	++

6.2 Knowledge gaps

The results obtainable with the mixtures of the three EOMs are not fully known. Experiments are underway with compost-digestate and biochar-digestate mixtures prepared and applied directly in the field. A second line of investigation is that of co-composting with digestate and biochar and concerns on the one hand the composting process, on the other the effect of the application in the field.

On the composting process side, it was observed that the mixture of biochar with bio wastes speeds up composting. On the application side, the mixture of biochar and digestate seems to reduce the load of *Clostridiaceae* in the amendment. The mechanism responsible for this result is not clear, but if confirmed, it would allow a wider use of digestate in forage crops of dairy farms.

Another gap is that of scale up from small-scale experiments to field application in the farm to improve the assessment of the practicality and cost efficiency when using digestate as soil amendments.

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